

**PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF
PTERIS BIAURITA L. FROM DARJEELING DISTRICT, WEST BENGAL**

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ABSTRACT

The present study includes preliminary phytochemical analysis and evaluation of antioxidant activity of *Pteris biaurita* L. The preliminary phytochemical screening performed with Hot water and Methanolic extracts of fronds with different maturity status. Free radical scavenging activity, DPPH assay and reducing power assay were performed following standard laboratory methods. Qualitative analysis showed the presence of secondary metabolites like cardiac glycosides, tannins, phenols, saponines, terpenoids and quinone etc. are present whereas alkaloids and glycosides are absent. Quantitative analysis of phenols and flavonoids showed their presence in detectable amount. Reducing power activity and DPPH scavenging activity along with carotenoid pigment content co-relate with the anti-oxidant properties of this plant in folk medicines.

Key Words : Phytochemical analysis, antioxidant activity, secondary metabolites.

INTRODUCTION

Pteridophytes are also known as vascular cryptogams generally classified as fern and fern allies' cover ground vegetation in many forest communities. Ferns comprise the dominant group amongst the Pteridophytes around the world, represented by 144 genera and about 1157 species in India (Chandra, 2000, Fraser Jenkins 2018). Ferns have been a source of food and medicines in many parts of the world. They are used in the Unani system of medicine from ancient times for the treatment of various human ailments (Uddin *et al.* 1998). The antioxidant properties of ferns were also reported by many workers (Skin. 2010). In addition to their antioxidant properties, the ferns also played an important role as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antitumor and antiviral agent (Chang *et al.* 2007). Darjeeling is biologically hot spots and rich in fern population which can be explored as a potential source of various herbal medicines.

The medicinal properties of plant groups are attributed by certain biochemical components and pigments in the plant. Many higher plants are major sources of useful secondary metabolites which are used in pharmaceuticals industries (Karuppusamy, 2009) but reports are few in case of ferns. In the present day scenario, the prospect of herbal medicine is noteworthy and screening of new medicinal plant for ethno botanical uses were carried out on pteridophytes by different workers for new medicine designing.

P. biaurita L. belongs to family Pteridaceae and commonly known as thin leaf Brake fern. It is found to grow in various habitats and has been used as folk medicine form ages.

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The aim of present study is to screen the phytochemical components and also to evaluate the antioxidant efficacy of some of these chemicals.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Plant Materials

The immature and mature fronds of *P. biaurita* L. were collected from different regions of Darjeeling district during the month July to September, 2020. The Plants were identified & authenticated by Pteridology and Palaeobotany Laboratory, University of North Bengal, India and preserved as a herbarium sp. Acc No-PTE-2103.

Extraction & Estimation of Chlorophyll

For extraction, 1 g of plant tissue was extracted in 80% acetone and the final volume was made up to 25 ml with 80% acetone (Harbone. 1973). For estimation, the extract was measured at O. D. values of 645 and 663 nm (Arnone. 1949) and chlorophyll a, chlorophyll b and total chlorophyll contents were calculated using the following formulae :

$$\text{Total chlorophyll} = (20.2 \times A_{645} + 8.02 \times A_{663}) \text{mg/g fresh weight}$$

$$\text{Chl}_A = (12.7 \times A_{663} - 2.69 \times A_{645}) \text{mg/g fresh weight}$$

$$\text{Chl}_B = (22.7 \times A_{645} - 4.68 \times A_{663}) \text{mg/g fresh weight}$$

Extraction and Estimation of carotenoid content

For extraction, 1g of plant tissue was extracted in 10 ml of 80% methanol and the final volume was made up to 10 ml with 80% methanol (Lihtenthaler. 1987). For estimation, the O. D. was measured at 480 nm, 645 nm and 663 nm and carotenoid content was calculated by using the formula :

$$\text{Carotenoids content} = A_{480} - (0.114 \times A_{663}) - 0.638 \times A_{645} \text{ mg/g plant tissue.}$$

Preparation of Plant Extract

The fresh plant materials were collected from field, washed thoroughly, dried and then a paste was prepared with the help of motor & pestle. After crushing the fronds segments were extracted separately with different solvent (hot water and methanol) in conical flask for 2 hours by reflux method. The supernatant of refluxed samples were isolated from residues by filtering through Whatman No. 1 filter paper. The excess solvent was removed by evaporation at 30°C and final concentration was taken as 500 mg/ml. The samples were then kept in refrigerator (4°C) for further use. (Kumar *et al.* 2009).

Qualitative Analysis

The phytochemical constituents were determined qualitatively by reference methods for alkaloids, cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, glycosides, quinone, phenol, steroids, saponins, tannins and terpenoids.

Test for alkaloids : To 5ml of frond extracts 5 ml of distilled water was added, followed by 2M HCL, until an acidic reaction occurs. To this 1 ml of Dragendroff's reagent

was added. Formation of orange or orange red precipitate produced immediately indicates the presence of alkaloids. (Kumar *et al.* 2009).

Test for cardiac glycoside : 0.5 ml of various frond extracts were evaporated and dissolved in 1 ml glacial acetic acid. One drop of FeCl_3 was then added. 1 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added by the side of the test tube. Brown ring was formed at the interface which indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides. (Ngbede *et al.* 2008)

Test for flavonoids : The frond extracts was dissolved in 5 ml of ethanol and to this 10 drops of dilute HCL followed by a small piece of magnesium were added. Formation of pink color, reddish or brown color indicates the presence of flavonoids. (Kumar *et al.* 2009).

Test for glycoside : The frond extract was hydrolyzed with HCL for few hours on water bath. To the hydrolysate, 1 ml of pyridine was added and a few drops of sodium nitroprusside solution were added and then it was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution appearance of pink to red color shows the presence of glycosides. (Kumar *et al.* 2009).

Test for Quinone : To 1 ml of frond extracts was treated with 1 ml of HCL, formation of red color indicates the presence of quinone. (Harbone JB. 1996)

Test for phenol : To 1 ml of frond extract, 3-4 drops of 3% ferric chloride solution was added. The formation of bluish black color indicates the presence of phenol. (Harbone JB. 1996)

Test for steroids : 0.5 ml fronds extracts were evaporated and dissolve in 2 ml chloroform. 2 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was introduced carefully by the side wall of the test tube. Formation of red color ring confirmed the presence of steroid. (Kumar *et al.*, 2009).

Test for saponin : 2 ml of double distilled water was added with 1 ml of each fronds extract. Few drops of olive oil were added and agitated. Formation of soluble emulsion indicated the presence of saponin. (Ngbede *et al.*, 2008).

Test for tannin : 5 ml of the extract and few drops of 1% lead acetate were added a yellow precipitate was formed indicates the presence of tannins. (Kumar *et al.*, 2009).

Test for terpenoids : To 2 ml of the fronds extract 2 ml acetic acid was added. Then concentrated sulphuric acid was added. Deep red color development showed the presence of terpenoids. (Yadav M. *et al.*, 2014).

Quantitative Analysis

a. Extraction and Estimation of total phenol

The phenolic compounds of frond extracts were determine by Folin-Ciocalteu method (Folin and Ciocalteu, 1927). A calibration curve was prepared using Methanolic gallic acid solution as a standard. Then total phenol content of different plant extracts of various concentrations were also measures following the same protocol. The total phenolic

content was expressed as mg of Gallic acid equivalent (GAE) per gram fresh weight (fw).

b. Total flavonoids content

The total flavonoids were determined using of Spectrophotometric Aluminum Chloride method (Sultana *et al.* 2009) 0.5 ml of the sample extracts (0-500 mg/ml) were mixed separately with 4 ml of distilled water in a test tube followed by the addition of 0.3 ml of 5% NaNO₂ solution. After 6 minutes, 0.3 ml of 10% AlCl₃ solution was added and the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 mins before the addition of 2 ml of 1M NaOH solution. About 2.4 ml of distilled water was finally added and the absorbance was measured immediately at 510 nm. The total flavonoid content in different extracts was calculated as quercetin equivalent (QE) per gram fresh weight.

c. DPPH radical scavenging assay

DPPH radical assay were done as per the method of Blois, 1958. The free radical scavenging capacity of the extracts was determined using DPPH. 0.2 ml methanol DPPH solution was mixed with 200 µl of serial dilution of (500-200) mg of leaf extracts and after 10 minutes the absorbance was read at 517 nm using spectrophotometer. A reaction mixture without test sample was considered as control.

The capacity to scavenge the radical was calculated using the equation :-

$$\text{DPPH scavenging effect (\%)} = [(\text{Abs.}_{\text{control}} - \text{Abs.}_{\text{sample}}) / \text{Abs.}_{\text{control}}] \times 100$$

Where, Abs. _{control} is the initial concentration of the stable DPPH radical without the test compound and Abs. _{sample} is the absorbance of the remaining concentration of DPPH in the presence of methanol. Then percentage inhibitions were plotted against concentration and from the graph, IC₅₀ was calculated.

d. Ferric reducing power Assay

The reducing power assay quantified by the method described by Oyaizu *et al.*, 1998 with minor modifications. Reaction mixture, containing 1ml of leaf extract added in 2.5 ml of sodium phosphate buffer, (0.2 M, pH 6.6), was incubated with potassium ferric cyanide (1% w/v) at 50°C for 20 mins. The reaction was terminated by the addition of tri-chloro acetic acid (TCA) solution (10%, w/v) and the mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 20 min. The supernatant was mixed with 2.5 ml of distilled water and 250 µl ferric chloride (0.1%, w/v) solutions and the absorbance measured at 700 nm. Increased absorbance of the reaction mixture indicated increased reducing power.

All the tests were performed three times and the mean value was recorded.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Pigment analysis showed that *P. biaurita* L. young and mature frond also contains Chlorophyll and Carotenoid pigments. (Table 1). Chlorophyll content at different maturity status signifies the photosynthetic ability, primary metabolite production ability and its

channelization to secondary metabolite production in plants for stress management.

TABLE 1 : Pigment Analysis of *P. biaurita* L.

Part used	Chl a mg/g fresh weight	Chl b mg/g fresh weight	Total chl mg/g fresh weight	Carotenoids mg/g fresh weight
<i>Pterisbiaurita</i> (Mature fronds)	9. 46	20. 1	29. 8	0. 58
<i>Pterisbiaurita</i> (Immature fronds)	3. 87	6. 57	10. 47	0. 47

Here in this experiment chl a/b ratio shows a decreased tendency. This could be an adaptive response for light harvesting maximization in case of shade loving plants like *Pteris* sp. Carotenoids act as photo protective agents, preventing the harmful photoreactions and as accessory light harvesting pigments. The carotene prevents chlorophyll and thylakoid

TABLE 2 : Phytochemical Analysis of *P. biaurita*

Phytochemical Compound	Plant Parts	AQ.	MeOH.
Alkaloids	IMF	–	–
	MF	–	–
Cardiac Glycosides	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Flavonoids	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Glycosides	IMF	–	–
	MF	–	–
Quinone	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Phenol	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Steroids	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Saponins	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Tannin	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+
Terpenoids	IMF	+	+
	MF	+	+

AQ = Aqueous extract, MeOH = Methanolic extract, + = activity, – = No activity
IMF = Immature Frond (Without sori), MF = Mature Frond (With sori)

membrane from the damage of absorbed energy by per-oxidation (Costache *et al.* 2012). The carotenoids present the fronds of this plant also take part in antioxidant defense system in human being and enhance the immune system via vitamin A synthesis as a natural one (Krunsky & Johnson 2005).

Phytochemical are the chemical which are derived from the plant source, generally effect health, but are not yet establish nutrients. They play role in plants but they are biologically active as well as use to cure various ailments. This components show anti-cancer, antioxidants, and anti-inflammatory activities. Different species of *Pteris* are worthy source of phytochemicals which can be used both in traditional and modern medicine (Singh *et al.* 2015). Pharmacological action depend greatly on the comprehensive effect of several various factors, including the extraction method, solvent type, extraction time, extraction temperature, pH, and liquid/solid ratio. So two different solvent were used here. In the present study, the aqueous and Methanolic extracts of immature and mature fronds of *P. biaurita* showed presence of ten phytochemicals in standard qualitative tests (Table 2). The results of phytochemical screening indicate the presence of secondary metabolites such as cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, quinones, phenols, steroids, saponins, tannins and terpenoids from methanol and hot water crude extract due to polar and non-polar activities of solvents. But the absence of alkaloids and glycosides is remarkably noticeable.

Many authors have reported that secondary metabolites are responsible for antioxidant activity of plants. Phenolic compounds as secondary metabolite of plants exhibit significant bioactivities. Several species of ferns has been considered as potential source of phenolic and flavonoids (Nurhasnawati *et al.*, 2019). Antioxidants properties and phytochemical analysis of *Pteris* along with others ferns has been reported previously (Jaishee & Chakraborty, 2014). The total phenol and flavonoids content in the tested plant sample in Hot water and methanol is given in Figure A & B.

The antioxidant activity of polyphenols is considered to be due to their properties as free radical terminators (Singh *et al.*, 2015). This study focuses on the estimation of total phenolic and flavonoid content for the determination of antioxidant activities of samples of *P. biaurita*. A good amount of phenolic content was observed in the sample and hot water extraction method was more effective than methanol ones.

The reducing ability of various extract of *P. biaurita* was determined with BHT (standard antioxidant) equivalent (Figure C & D). Higher BHT equivalent value indicates higher reducing capacity of tested plant samples and greater antioxidant potential. Both methanol and hot water extracts showed significantly higher DPPH scavenging activity in case of *P. biaurita* extracts, but at different maturity of fronds. Results showed that hot water extracts performed quite well in DPPH assay with higher inhibition percentage as compared to methanol extracts in both case of the frond extracts. Extracts of fronds displayed significantly higher DPPH Scavenging activity (IC_{50} value ranges from 2.97mg/ml–1.47mg/ml).

FIGURE A

FIGURE B

FIGURE C

FIGURE D

Reductonea special class of organic compounds is generally associated with the reducing properties which may be shown to exert antioxidant action by breaking the free radical chain by donating a hydrogenatom. This experiment was performed for the determination of reducing capacity (reducing power assay) through “Fe³⁺- Fe²⁺ transportation” technique in presence of extract was observed and it shows a positive result.

CONCLUSION

Analysis of phytochemicals and antioxidants comprises the sample of *P. biaurita* collected from Darjeeling District revealed that secondary metabolites like cardiac glycosides, tannins, phenols, saponines, terpenoids and quines etc. are present whereas alkaloids and glycosides are absent in all samples collected. The study also conducted for the qualitative as well as quantitative analysis of phenolic compounds content which has an exponential increase in Pteridophytes research in recent years for its antimicrobial activity. A good amount of phenolic is present in this particular plant species. The study also conducted with the reference of reducing power activity and DPPH scavenging activity along with carotenoid content which are related with the anti-oxidant properties and is also attributed to its multi-therapeutic characteristics in folk medicine. Thus this finding suggest that *P. biaurita* might be useful in development of raw materials for future medicine and health care products for aging and chronic diseases they are rich source of phenolic and flavonoids which are also good source of antioxidants. However, further study is essential to characterize and isolate bioactive compounds from this important fern.

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